
Indonesia's Role in the Defense Sector Globalization Process

Era Nuansa Mediana¹, Sri Sundari², Haetami³

¹(Student in Defense Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

²(Lecturer in Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

³(Lecturer in Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT : Globalization is a worldwide process without boundaries marked by the rapid flow of information, communication, and technology. The result of globalization is the emergence of international cooperation, including in the field of defense. Today, technology has been used to strengthen the defense systems of various countries, including Indonesia. Strengthening the defense sector supported by the availability of national resources will be a valuable asset in creating community welfare. To achieve this, the government needs to establish mutually beneficial cooperation with other countries. Through a qualitative study, namely a review of books, journals, and other important documents, this journal aims to explain how Indonesia's role in the globalization process of the defense sector and the areas that are the impact of defense. Therefore, to realize this, several things are carried out, including strengthening the national defense posture in supporting Indonesia's participation in the international world, actively playing a role in global contestation in the defense sector in particular, and parliamentary support in the process of allocating the total defense budget.

KEYWORDS: Globalization, Defense, Indonesia's Role

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization is a comprehensive or global process where everyone is not bound by country or regional boundaries, meaning that every individual can connect and exchange information anywhere and anytime through electronic or print media. Globalization can make a country smaller because of the ease of communication between countries in various fields of information exchange and trade.

There are several factors that cause globalization, including the development of information and communication technology, international economic cooperation, and the advancement of science and technology in all fields, which cause the globalization process to accelerate. Globalization has an impact on the increasing number of developments, the ease of communication, the improvement in the economic sector to be more productive, effective, and efficient. The standard of living of people increases and spurs the improvement of self-quality.

The era of globalization brings very rapid changes. Advances in information technology have been able to be utilized in strengthening the defense sector, which is manifested in defense equipment and non-defense equipment. In an effort to increase the index of military strength, Indonesia from a demographic, geographical, and sociographic perspective is very profitable. However, there are still many indicators that must be met to become one of the world's military elites. The role of several defense diplomacy strategies and approaches is very important. The availability of abundant natural resources becomes valuable capital along with its human resources. The defense development process that is built from many sides will benefit.

The government and stakeholders need to establish a lot of mutually beneficial cooperation. The aim is to optimize economic, human, social, and cultural resources for the creation of usefulness. The formulated strategy must be made with the aim of creating branding as a result of infiltration in the defense sector, increasing awareness of defense strengthening, and increasing welfare. For this reason, this article discusses the globalization process of the defense sector, Indonesia's role in the era of globalization in the renewal and strengthening of the defense sector, the importance of defense doctrine, and the government's efforts in defense strengthening diplomacy.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1 Globalization

Globalization in the Big Indonesian Dictionary means the process of entering the world scope (Language Development and Development Agency, 2021). In simple terminology, it means that Indonesia is heading into a global order. Globalization, according to Dhofier, is the loss of geographical boundaries in the context of the development of values and ideologies (Dhofier, 1985). Meanwhile, according to Dede Nurohman, globalization is a big current that is thrown by many factors, especially world politics and economics, that hit and affect all aspects of life in the state, culture, and religion (Nurohman, 2017). Globalization basically has no single interpretation. Globalization marks the emergence of a new civilization with/in business called the sharing economy. In the context of geoeconomics, Soilen suggests steps to make scientific progress, then teach that progress to others and incorporate new knowledge into new products to be sold, preferably abroad. With the new profits obtained, reinvest them in science, so that the process continues (Priyono, 2017).

The process of globalization creates patterns, including the characteristics of global association. Haidar Daulaby argues that in general the global associations that occur today and in the future can be formulated as follows:

- a. There is a shift from ideological and political conflicts to competition in trade, investment, and information; from a balance of power to a balance of interest.
- b. The relationship between countries or nations is structurally changing from dependency towards interdependency; primordial relationships take on a nature depending on the bargaining position.
- c. Geographical boundaries have almost lost their operational meaning. The strength of a country and community in their interactions with the state (other communities) is determined by their ability to take advantage of comparative advantages and competitive advantages.
- d. Competition between countries is colored by wars between masters of high technology. Each country is forced to provide large funds for research and development.
- e. The creation of a world culture that tends to be mechanistic and efficient does not respect values and norms that are considered economically inefficient (Daulaby and Harahap, 2004).

2.2 National Defense

National Defense, according to the Regulation of the Minister of Defense Number 16 of 2012 concerning the Policy for the Integration of the National Defense Components is as follows:

"State defense is all efforts to uphold the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation. The national defense effort is carried out by taking into account the dynamics of the threats faced. The development of the strategic environment always brings changes to the complexity of threats, both military threats and non-military threats. National defense functions to realize and defend the entire territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia as a defense unit. National defense is organized by the

government and prepared early with the national defense system through building and fostering the capability and deterrence of the state and nation as well as overcoming any threats".

The spirit of national defense arises from what is called the doctrine of national defense. In the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2014, it is explained that the National Defense Doctrine is essentially a teaching on fundamental principles that provide direction for the management of defense resources. The Doctrine of National Defense is the basic principles that are believed to be true, extracted from the values of the nation's struggle and past experiences to be used as guidelines or teachings in developing the concept of national defense and security. The doctrine arose from a sense of nationalism in order to preserve the integrity of a country's sovereignty. Nationalism is considered a trigger for enthusiasm in the love of one's country.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted using a qualitative approach with descriptive analysis methods through data collection, which is described in detail and regularly updated. Data collection techniques through documentation are carried out through reviewing and/or browsing several books, journals, printed or electronic documents, and other sources of data or information deemed relevant to the research or study (Supriyadi, 2016).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The approach to the problem of Indonesia's role in the globalization of the defense sector, how important the defense doctrine is, and the government's efforts in defense-strengthening diplomacy are both homework and very important tasks. The term "globalization of the defense sector" appears to be interpreted as a process to answer the challenges of the times for national defense. Linking defense closely with today's actual conditions is how the state is able to provide the latest supply of technology and information to strengthen defense to face threats, both military and non-military. The increasingly heated global competition makes geopolitics and geostrategy difficult to predict. The forces contained in the world's military are also becoming increasingly difficult to predict due to the increasingly sophisticated defense equipment of each. This means Indonesia has to carry out an update on defense support, including the military component itself and its non-military components.

In order to display the superiority of the defense posture, the main weapon system and the defense industry need to be optimized. Both BUMN and BUMS must work together. The linkage in the supply relationship of the materials for the manufacture of defense equipment makes analysis easier. BUMN and BUMS are industries that make defense equipment products that are supported by domestically available production factors, which include land, human resources, and the ability of domestic experts.

Furthermore, regarding the importance of the defense doctrine, it is clear that this is an obligation. National identity, nationalism, and patriotism must always be cultivated. Without this doctrine, the state will be easily confused by various issues that cause division. Therefore, the government also plays a major role in collaborating with countries that have produced defense equipment technology so that technology transfer and defense industry knowledge can be absorbed more quickly.

The basis for re-strengthening the defense industry is the impact of the 1998 crisis that hit all sectors. At that time, it is hoped that the existence of the defense industry will also provide economic benefits. In 2005, the state redesigned the defense industry as a national strategic industry. The steps taken by the government are solely to reduce dependence on the supply of defense equipment from abroad. With the enactment of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2012 concerning the Defense Industry, the existing domestic defense industry received a clear legal umbrella. The reason is that every defense industry, both state-owned and private, is recognized and protected by the government.

The law also stipulates that parties involved in the production of defense equipment must work together to achieve an optimally developed defense industry. There is a high expectation that if the synergy is well established, there will be healthy competition between private businesses in the modernization of defense equipment components.

Indonesia itself must also be sure that the products produced by the domestic defense industry today are no less competitive, but are able to emerge as a supplier of the world's elite defense equipment. A series of achievements in the international arms race and the sale of defense equipment to various countries is proof that Indonesia has a role in the globalization of the defense sector and is capable of becoming a respected military force. The direction of cooperation must be accompanied by technology transfer, which must be carried out intensively.

Listed in the 2018-2019 Indonesian Defense Industry Directory book, there are eight state-owned defense industries and 33 privately-owned defense industries. This indicates that the defense industry is a strategic industry, in addition to contributing to the fulfillment of defense equipment as a defense and national security, they also capture great economic value from it. In line with Dede Nurohman's opinion, which states that globalization is a large current arising from politics and economics that can affect multiple sectors, the concept of developing the defense industry (modernity and independence of the defense industry) is part of the globalization of the defense sector.

4.1 Defense Posture Supports Indonesia's Role

Looking at the concept idea by Dede Nurohman, economic globalization is defined as a process of economic activity and trade where countries around the world become a market force that is increasingly integrated with no barriers to national territorial boundaries. The positive impacts of economic globalization are:

- a. Global production can be increased.
- b. Increase the prosperity of the people in a country.
- c. Expanding the market for domestic products.
- d. Can get more capital and better technology.
- e. Provide additional funds for economic development.

The development of economic globalization marks the development of the global world, which has an impact on the defense sector. Indonesia, which has strategic space and sufficient resources, has high demands and expectations on the defense industry in order to increase the capacity and quality of defense equipment. Many efforts need to be made to catch up with regard to technology, starting with cooperation with technology transfer agreements and innovation in weapons equipment. Modernization in terms of defense equipment is a necessity that must be implemented.

Figure 1. Elements of Defense Resources

Source: Indonesian Defense Strategy Book, 2015

In the 2019 Special Edition Wira book describes an image sourced from the 2015 Indonesian Strahan Book that defense resources are conceptualized as national resources that are transformed into elements of national strength. This "national power" is divided into elements of military and non-military defense forces. In my view, this is a component that forms the national defense posture. Law Number 34 of 2004 explains that the state defense posture is a form of the appearance of the national defense force, which is reflected in the integration of strength, capability, and deployment of national resources arranged in the national defense system, consisting of the main components, Komcad, and Komduk.

Relevant to this, the presentation of the Head of the Ministry of Defense's Head of Research and Development in Yogyakarta on May 10, 2008 explained that the phase III (2020-2024) posture development is "the realization of a professional TNI with strong reserve components and supporting components; the realization of synergies in performance in the fields of security, intelligence, and intelligence; and effective counterintelligence coupled with reliable industrial capabilities." The function of this development is to form the national defense posture, which is the capital that plays a role in the globalization of defense. The minimum indicators that must be met are the defense strategy, the posture of both military and non-military forces, and the doctrines that support defense forces.

4.2 Indonesia's Role in the Global Contest

The arms race is a positive thing to build the independence of each country's industry and as a form of increasing defense. The majority of the world's countries reduce spending on defense budgets, in contrast to the Southeast Asian region, which is trending toward growing military spending. According to matamatapolitik.com data, Indonesia and Thailand are the highest Southeast Asian countries in terms of spending, at 10% from year to year.

High spending means weapons are also increasingly equipped. Common weapons include ships, tanks, helicopters, fighter jets, and submarines. Many observers have expressed their opinion about the high dynamic phenomenon of countries in the Southeast Asian region. Observers consider that future prospects related to the arms race will provide a broader context for changes. The changes include strategic uncertainty regarding the rise of China, anxiety about America's withdrawal from the Southeast Asian region, and the persistence of various flash points between ASEAN countries.

Southeast Asian countries spend a lot of their budgets on modernizing their weapons systems. Changes that occur in the dynamics of weapons have a broader trend. The majority of the region's militaries are undergoing a strategic reorientation away from an exclusive focus on counter-insurgency and

domestic stability and towards external defense, power projection, and conventional warfare. This has increased since the uncertainty in Southeast Asia about the rise of China and the impact it will have on regional security due to the US-China geostrategic impact.

According to the latest SIPRI data, the development of the military capacity of Southeast Asian countries seems to signal an increase in military strength until an arms race occurs. The study found that the reasons behind the increase in military power included external driving factors, including regional tensions due to China-US military activities. Regional tensions often occur due to the overlapping of the outer water zones of several countries (EEZ), plus the very active Chinese military invasion. Things like this should be responded to well by the Southeast Asian region. Existing military strength needs to be projected towards meeting these needs and meeting those challenges. Things that can be done, for example, are joint military operations and maritime order exercises by Southeast Asian countries. From here, each country can measure the advantages and disadvantages of each. In addition, future military optimization also involves resolving disputes and global strategic issues that continue to influence and have an impact on security. The strategic environmental issues are fluctuations in world oil prices, climate change, the economic crisis, the dominance of developed countries, and changes in world power.

4.3 The Role of Parliament in Influencing the Defense Budget Allocation Process in the Republic of Indonesia

One of the efforts that are part of the national goal is that the state is obliged to strengthen the national defense system by placing the people as the owners of a vital role. The universal people's defense and security system places the TNI and POLRI as the main forces and the people as the supporting forces.

In the past, Soekarno said that the Indonesian armed forces could not be separated from the Indonesian people, especially since the origin of the armed forces came from the people, the position of the armed forces was part of the people, and the aim was to ensure the security of the people. Bung Karno also emphasized that the importance of the concept of Indonesian defense and security stems from the culture and geographical characteristics of Indonesia. In his speech on May 7, 1953 at the University of Indonesia, Bung Karno emphasized 2 things, namely:

- a. Indonesian nationalism is not narrow nationalism but nationalism that reflects humanity (humanism, internationalism).
- b. Indonesia's independence does not only aim to make a politically and economically sovereign country, but also to develop its own personality or culture, which is *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika*.

Based on a thick history of emphasizing the importance of supporting the state defense and security system, the parliament, through its legislative role, supports the 21st century universal people's defense system (*sishankamrata*), which is carried out through the legislative function, the function of determining the State Budget, the supervisory function, and the role of parliamentary diplomacy. Through the legislative function, efforts to support national defense, including *sishankamrata*, are carried out through the formulation of several laws, including:

- a. Law No. 5 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Law No. 15 of 2003 concerning Stipulation of Government Regulations in Lieu of Law No. 1 of 2002 concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Terrorism.
- b. Law No. 23 of 2019 concerning Management of State Defense Resources (PSDN).
- c. The Omnibus Law of the Bill on Job Creation (Defense Cluster), which was passed into law in the Plenary Session of the Indonesian Parliament on October 5, 2020.

In terms of the supervisory and diplomatic functions, the DPR RI is committed to providing strategic input on various defense-related policies, namely:

- a. On the issue of the South China Sea, Commission I of the Indonesian House of Representatives provided support to the Ministry of Defense for the addition of the fleet and maximizing border patrols by supporting and approving the grant of 14 Drone Scan Eagles and the upgrade of three Bell 412 Helicopters from the United States Government, to strengthen the naval defense equipment.
- b. Handling COVID-19, Commission I of the DPR RI appreciates the commitment and role of the TNI through OMSP from the beginning of handling the pandemic to the current phase of economic recovery. Especially for the TNI, the Indonesian House of Representatives provides full support for the operation of the TNI hospital ship fleet on islands that lack access to health, provides support for the task of assisting in the deployment of the TNI AL Hospital Vessels, namely KRI Soeharso and KRI Semarang, currently operating to assist repatriation of Indonesian citizens in Malaysia, as well as in transporting medical aid materials from Singapore to be brought to Galang Island.
- c. Modernization of defense equipment and support for the advancement of the defense industry, the Indonesian House of Representatives, especially Commission I, is committed to encouraging the completion of the MEF, which is currently entering the final strategic plan for the realization of the TNI's essential force, and is committed to encouraging the fulfillment of defense equipment needs, which are realized with budget support through an increase in the 2020 defense budget of Rp. 131 trillion (Maharani, 2020).

V. CLOSING

5.1. Conclusion

- a. To play a role in the defense globalization process, Indonesia must have a strong defense posture supported by great defense resources. In addition to efforts to modernize defense equipment and improve the welfare of soldiers, other indicators that are no less important are the defense strategy, the posture of both military and non-military forces, and the doctrines that support defense forces.
- b. To strengthen itself in the global process itself, Indonesia must appear in international contestations. Both joint military exercises, defense equipment transactions, arms races, and being sensitive to international strategic issues and trying to reduce physical wars so that they don't arise.
- c. Indonesia's sustainability in playing a role in the globalization process of defense requires moral and material government support in the form of a budget and diplomacy of technology transfer cooperation.

5.2 Recommendation

- a. The government must seriously observe maintaining a very strategic defense industry. The increasing number of privately owned defense industries greatly assists the government's defense industry business, for that the government needs to give appreciation in the form of disbursement of funds which can be used for massive development and encourage healthy competition in efforts to improve technology.
- b. The government must rework the current very small percentage of the defense budget.
- c. Diplomatic efforts and marketing of defense equipment must continue to be carried out so that production does not stop and the economy of the defense sector continues to run.

REFERENCES

Books:

- [1] Priyono, Juniawan, *GeopolitikGeostrategiGeoekonomi*(Bogor, Unhan Press, 2017).
- [2] Daulaby, Haidar andHarahapSyahrin, *Perguruan Tinggi Islam di Era Globalisasi*(Yogyakarta, Tiara WacanaYogya, 2004)
- [3] Dhofier, Zamakhsyari, *TradisiPesantren: Studi Tentang Pandangan Hidup Kiai*(Jakarta, LP3ES, 1985)
- [4] Media Informasi Kementerian Pertahanan, *Eksistensi TNI dalam menghadapi Ancaman Militer dan Nir Militer Multidimensional di Era Milenial* (Jakarta, Biro Humas Setjenkemhan, 2019)

Journal Papers:

- [5] Supriyadi, S, KomunitasPraktisi: Solusi AlternatifBerbagi Pengetahuan AntarPustakawan, Lentera Pustaka: *Jurnal Kajian Ilmu Perpustakaan, Informasi Dan Kearsipan*, 2(2), 2016, 85. <https://ejournal.undip.ac.id/index.php/lpustaka/article/view/13476>.

Other References:

- [6] National Seminar Material by Mrs. Puan Maharani (Chairman of the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia) in a Scientific Oration at the Defense University of the Republic of Indonesia on October 26, 2020.
- [7] Language Development and Cultivation Agency. 2021. in <https://kbbi.web.id/globalisasi>.
- [8] Nurohman, Dede. Globalization of Islamic Economic Perspective . The Power Point was delivered at the East Java Islamic Economics and Business Student National Forum on September 30, 2017.
- [9] Regulation of the Minister of Defense Number 16 of 2012 concerning the Policy for the Integration of National Defense Components.
- [10] Indonesia Law No. 34 of 2004 About the Indonesian National Army.